

PR106 had less than 20% damage in one replication but more than 60% of its plot was completely destroyed in another replication. The same was true for PR445, PR560, PR561, and PR563.

A survey conducted by the Indian Directorate of Quarantine, Plant Protection, and Storage also revealed hopperburn on IR8 on farmers' fields in the Punjab in 1978. An objective of our future rice breeding programs is to develop WBPH-resistant varieties. □

Evaluation of rice strains for resistance to gall midge and leaf roller

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Rice entries received from the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project were screened for resistance to gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* and leaf roller

Hopperburn in PR558 rice, caused by WBPH in 1978 at the Rice Research Station, Kapurthala, India.

Cnaphalocrosis medinalis in a field trial laid out in a randomized block design at Madurai Agricultural College Farm in

1977-78. Of the 265 entries evaluated, 20 had minimum incidence of gall midge and leaf roller (see table). IET 6181, 6286, 6293, and 6195, on which the incidence of both gall midge and leaf roller was much lower than that on the susceptible varieties, appear to have some resistance to both insects. □

Rice entries resistant to gall midge and leaf roller, mean of two replications in 3 periods, Madurai, India.

IET no.	Designation	Parents	Tillers (%) affected by gall midge	Leaves (%) affected by leaf roller
<i>Resistant to both gall midge and leaf roller</i>				
6181	WGL20691	CR44/W12708	0.9	7.1
6286	CR 95-181-2	Leaung 152/IR8	0	9.3
6293	WGL 26445	—	0	8.8
6295	RNR 32341	—	0.4	7.9
<i>Resistant to gall midge</i>				
4600	RP 872-1-2	Cauvery/W12787	0	—
5700	IR2071-636-5-5	IR24/CR94-13	0.8	—
5703	HYN 17-5-4	Hoyoku/Zinya	0.5	—
5981	OR 100-7	Kumar/Bala	0.9	—
5116	RP894-5-1-5-4	CR44-35/W12708	0.5	—
5233	RP872-20-4-3-4	Cauvery/W12787	0.4	—
5711	RP974-173-4	Sona/RP9-4	0	—
6257	1140-47-2-46-19	—	0.3	—
2911	RPW 6-17	IR8/Siam 29	0.7	—
3347	ORS 46 1	Leaung 152//IR8*2	0	—
3354	RP350-57-1-1	820862/820916	0.2	—
3356	RP352-28-1-1-4	IR8/PTB18//Eswarakora/IR8	0	—
3362	RP9-10-3-2-1-1	IR8/W1251	0.7	—
6287	CR 95-26-1	Leaung 152/IR8	0.7	—
6292	WGL 26442	—	0.3	—
—	RPW 6-13	—	0.7	—
<i>Susceptible check</i>				
Jaya			17.2	60.1
Pankaj			12.0	—

Outbreak of rice thrips in Kuttanadu, Kerala, India

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The usual farming practice in Kuttanadu is to grow a single rice crop (locally called *punja*) from October to February. Farmers have recently attempted to grow a second rice crop from April to September, which is almost free of serious insect problems.

The rice thrip *Buliothrips biformis* has only recently become a serious punja-season pest, especially on the late crop. The transplanted crop suffered a serious thrip outbreak in May and June 1978. The main symptoms were leaf rolling and drying at the leaf tips. In severe infestations the plants were stunted and the lower leaves killed.

Observations of 15 varieties and lines